

LIST OF THE ERA-Interim EVALUATION RUNS OF THE MED-CORDEX BASELINE RUNS

version 0: S. Somot, January 2020

version 1: S. Somot, March 2021

version 2: S. Somot, January 2022, merging Phase 1 and Phase 2 run lists + last updates

Version 3: S. Somot, I. Parras-Berrocal, 20 April 2026, update the model names to match with the literature and official IPCC Interactive Atlas naming

In Med-CORDEX, 18 evaluation runs driven by ERA-Interim have been performed with 18 different RCSM configurations and by 10 different institutes. This includes phase 1 and phase 2 runs.

Simulations done, Simulations in preparation

Model Naming, model_id	Period	Status	Last update
CNRM-RCSM4	1980-2013	done <i>ref: Sevault et al. 2014</i>	2022-01-20
CNRM-RCSM6	1980-2019	done (after 19 years of spinup), <i>ref: Darmaraki et al. 2019b, GRL</i>	2022-01-20
ENEA-PROTHEUSv2	1982-2010	done	
ENEA-RegCM-ES	1979-2015	done	
CLMcom-GUF-CCLM-NEMO	1980-2012	done	
CLMcom-GUF-CCLM5-0-9-NEMOMED12-3-6	1979-2016	done	2019-11-24
LMD-LMDZ4-NEMOMED8v1	1979-2019	done	
LMD-LMDZ4-NEMOMED8v2	1979-2018	done	2024-01
IPSL-MORCEMED	1989-2013	done	

IPSL-RegIPSL	1979-2016	done	2019-11-20
CMCC-CCLM4-21-NEMOMFSv1 (50km)	1980-2011	done	
CMCC-CCLM4-21-NEMOMFSv2 (12km)	1979-2018	done	2019-11-15
UBEL-EBUPOM2c	1989-2008	done	
ITU-RegESM1	1979-2012	done	
ITU-RegESM1.2	1979-2012	done	2021-03-29
AWI-GERICS-ROM44	1980-2012	done	
AWI-GERICS-ROM22	1980-2012	done	2019-11-28
AWI-GERICS-ROM11	1980-2012	done	
INSTM-LMD-ROMS-MED	1979-2009	done	

REFERENCES:

- Darmaraki S., Somot S., Sevault F., Nabat P. (2019) Past Variability of Mediterranean Sea Marine Heatwaves. *GRL*, 46, 9813-9823, doi:10.1029/2019GL082933. *Special Section: The CNRM Climate and Earth System Models for CMIP6*
- Sevault, F., Somot, S., Alias, A., Dubois, C., Lebeaupin-Brossier, C., Nabat, P., ... & Decharme, B. (2014). A fully coupled Mediterranean regional climate system model: design and evaluation of the ocean component for the 1980–2012 period. *Tellus A: Dynamic Meteorology and Oceanography*, 66(1), 23967.